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Lifelong Learning and VET: Towards Understanding the Influence of Societal Eco-Systems on Learning Across the Lifespan

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Abstract

The impetus of this presentation is to facilitate discussion to reflect on a range of complex interdependencies between lifelong learning (LLL) and vocational education and training (VET), specifically considering the role and influence of societal ecosystems on learning across the lifespan. The VET system, as a means to integrate individuals into the labour market and improve their life chances, has become one of most integral configurations of LLL, fostering social inclusion, participation and skills development across a range of social spaces and contexts. The central question posed by this presentation aims to consider how the concept of ecosystems can be used to better understand both individual learning paths and the potential of institutional cooperation in VET. The discussion further considers how educational services could be made more effective in supporting LLL within workplace, educational and societal ecosystems at different levels (i.e. macro, meso and micro levels).

Introduction

Fresh trends in economic and social development have contributed to the changes in perception of learning through life, the skills required by contemporary learning spaces and the ways that adults engage with a range of networks, contexts and spaces. The position and role of the learner, central to these developments, needs to be better understood, taking into account the complex interdependencies and emerging methods of communication between different contexts and environments.

Vocational and work-based learning has long been recognised as a crucial component of national and international strategies for LLL (Evans, 2009; Aspin et al, 2012; Malloch et al, 2011), which aim to bring about inclusion and lifelong learning of adults across their life span. In this respect, the VET system, as a means to integrate individuals into society and the labour market, has been an important element of LLL and inclusion approaches (e.g. Evans and Niemeyer, 2004). Engaging adults through different forms of LLL has been strongly related to addressing their specific needs and requirements to facilitate their participation in social, economic and civic/political life in their relevant contexts and spaces, both underpinned and influenced by relevant ecosystems and ecologies.

The central points of this discussion as well as questions that we pose in this presentation originate from the 2017 European VET Skills LLL meeting, and relates to the concept of ecosystems and the ways that this concept can be used to better understand individual learning

paths and the potential of institutional cooperation in VET, which is relevant to the emerging findings of the ongoing H2020 project EduMAP¹.

How can the concept of ecosystem be understood?

The concept of ecosystem has been employed in different disciplines as a tool to provide a better understanding of a range of interactions and interdependencies in a variety of contexts, spaces and environments, and there is no universal definition of what constitutes an ecosystem. The definition offered by Hodgson and Spours (2018) provides a helpful framework for a better understanding of how individuals navigate different contexts and spaces while engaging in a range of interactions and communication, and how the spaces and contexts interact and connect through institutional and other types of cooperation and networking. Furthermore, they define a social ecosystem as an evolving place-based, comprehensive social formation focused on the connected worlds of working, living and learning. (Hodgson & Spours, 2018). In this interpretation, connecting the worlds of working, living and learning across the lifespan, happens through a range of cooperation among networks and may take place at macro, meso or micro levels, involving communication and collaboration between key actors. The related concept of communicative ecologies helps to better understand the complex methods of communication and networking in the context of learning through life. In the H2020 EduMAP project communicative ecologies are interpreted as complex systems of communication, media and information flows in a community or group of people (EduMap, 2017). A communicative ecologies approach provides a way of thinking about the ways in which information and communication flows between people and through infrastructures and institutions at they learn through the life course.

Macro level

At macro level, the consideration of wider discourses and ecosystems may contribute to a better understanding of the ways in which society can engage with enhancing LLL and developing vocational education for adults. One influential social discourse emphasises the economic justification of LLL, where the value of LLL is in acquiring job-related skills and competences, i.e. skills that would enable individuals to succeed in the job market. The findings from the current H2020 project (EduMap) indicate that the first discourse provides a very powerful context and rationale for the development of lifelong learning and adult education across Europe. Moving adults into work and enabling them to learn skills required by the contemporary labour market has been considered as one of the most significant prerequisites of adult education courses. Evans (2009) further argues that LLL is more than simply about the intrinsic value of learning or developing the skills and competences required by the labour market. Repositioning adult education within LLL requires a shared philosophy of the purposes and benefits of lifelong learning, which relate to the expansion of human capabilities rather than for merely economic development. Such an approach presupposes that learning is rooted in interactions in the social and material environment as well as in the ways in which people connect new experiences to their prior learning (Illeris, 2009, 2011). Therefore, the consideration of the ways through which institutional and wider societal dynamics might enhance LLL and improve adults' life chances requires a deeper understanding from a socio-ecological standpoint.

¹ EduMap (2016-2018) The project is funded under the European Union's Horizon 2020, Research and Innovation programme, Inclusive, Innovative and Reflective Societies under grant agreement No 693388. This paper reflects only the author's views and the European Union is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

Meso level

Institutional communication and cooperation are central to the developmental processes of LLL. The conclusions from the EduMap project indicate that communicative practices are highly context-dependent. This applies not only to a specific country context or field of adult education, but can also be relevant for considering different LLL-related programmes within one organisation. The diversity of contexts is also important when considering whether communicative practices can be linked to a specific organisation, and often depends on the interplay between professionals from different organisations. Cooperation is valued among VET providers and help them to shape, develop and redevelop educational programmes for adults.

A key issue is how can we make cooperation between VET providers and other sectors and stakeholders (e.g. higher education, policy makers) work better? These issues that need to be addressed more effectively at the meso level, while at the same time being informed by the micro and macro levels. The findings of the EduMap project have indicated that better collaboration within the same organisation, as well as with external institutions, is one of the key dimensions of a successful programme. Communicative ecosystems and networks play a crucial role in this process.

Micro level

Including analysis of individual and collective learning paths is critically important to responding to these questions. For example, if vocational schools are to provide a stronger platform for LLL, it is important to better understand how vocational schools and initiatives for young adults can build self-esteem. This type of problem has to be understood from the bottom up, not through our assumptions about what the problems are but from the points of view of participants – including students, teachers and employers. Including research at the micro-level often problematises policy responses in order to improve them. Not only shared understandings of the participants but also links and learning paths from pre-school to adults and beyond to later life have to be understood if we are serious about transforming vocational education. Understanding the roots of vocational learning from the early years and growing from them is a multi-level research challenge that explores the interrelationships between the micro, meso and macro levels. Communication challenges, linked to limited confidence, skills or awareness, are another indication of the struggles faced by some young people. An overall key finding emerging from the EduMap project is the importance of a match between learner needs, motivations and aspirations with adult education/VET programme content, methods and contexts of delivery. The influence of relevant ecosystems and ecologies needs to be taken into account.

A socio-ecological approach requires the development of more participatory research – communication ecologies operate through networks that build these shared understandings and develop them into interventions. Building shared understandings of the perspectives and capabilities of participants in VET is one of the core elements. Teachers and trainers as social actors play a key mediating role in the openness of institutions to new ideas about VET and vocational learning throughout the life course

Questions for discussion

The following central research question and sub-questions were identified:

How can concepts of ecosystems be used to better understand learning paths and the potential of institutional cooperation in VET, in order to find out how to make educational services more effective in supporting lifelong learning within business, educational and societal ecosystems?

- How can the concept of ecosystems facilitate an understanding of the dynamics at macro level? How are social and economic changes impacting on the conception of VET?
- How can we make cooperation between VET providers and other sectors and stakeholders at meso level (e.g. higher education, policy makers) work better?

- how can we ensure a match between learner needs, motivations and aspirations with adult education/VET programme content, methods and contexts of delivery? How can recognition of skills and competences be expanded to better recognise multiple forms of expertise in action?

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Minutes

The discussion that followed the presentation emphasised a number of significant issues that need to be taken into consideration and further explored when researching aspects of lifelong learning (LLL) and vocational education and training (VET). The following questions were considered:

1. How can the concept of ecosystems facilitate an understanding of these dynamics? How are social and economic changes impacting on the conception of VET?
2. How can we make cooperation between VET providers and other sectors and stakeholders (e.g. higher education, policy-makers) work better?
3. How can we ensure a match between learners' needs, motivations and aspirations with adult education/VET programme content, methods and contexts of delivery?
4. How can recognition of skills and competences be expanded to better recognise multiple forms of expertise in action?

These questions were formulated to facilitate discussion and offered an initial impetus for consideration of the key issues related to the questions above. The discussion that followed drew on these questions as starting points, leading to the development of emerging cross-cutting themes which have indicated overlaps and interconnections between key points highlighted by the questions.

The concept of VET and LLL

Considering the concept of VET and LLL was recognised as an important starting point. The discussion stimulated valuable reflections on the interrelationships between VET and LLL. These two concepts need further exploration in the context of current developments and discourses. As has been noted, identifying some common elements of LLL and VET could contribute to enhancing conceptual clarity and a better understanding of both common and distinguishing features between LLL and VET. VET is an integral part of the LLL discourse, providing opportunities for both acquiring occupationally related skills and facilitating social inclusion, employability and active citizenship.

The discussion has indicated that in today's LLL and VET programmes, there are some important challenges that need to be addressed across all levels (micro, meso and macro):

1. Understanding the nature and purposes of LLL is of crucial significance: e.g. training for lifelong learning (training to learn how to learn) versus training for a job.
2. The challenge highlighted by the discussion is how to facilitate not only learning for employability, inclusion and citizenship, but also developing an environment that would support a 'Joy to learn' concept. This is an important prerequisite that could be one of the contextual factors for the development of a meaningful learning environment.

One of the main concerns raised within the discussion related to the questions of the extent to which different political and social discourses and contexts may affect and shape approaches to LLL and VET. For example, the economic agenda (training for specific jobs rather than training to learn) may hinder the LLL outlook for learners.

Ecosystems and discourses

The discussion has suggested that the ecosystem approach has the potential for helping researchers to better understand different types of interactions in a range of contexts and environments, offering a systematic approach to exploring the nature of interrelations and communications. However, the concept of ecosystems has often been conceptually contested, and there is no universal definition of what constitutes an ecosystem. The challenges associated with the use of this concept in research have been identified, as follows:

1. There is no clear distinction in the literature between related concepts such as communicative ecosystems, networking, ecologies and social discourses. These concepts need to be better defined and the relationships between the concepts need to be explored and understood.
2. Exploring ecosystems in addition to context and localism and the three levels (micro, meso and macro) could contribute to a better conceptual understanding of this notion, as these are in constant flux.
3. Is ‘social/societal ecosystem’ the best term to describe the links between living, working and learning (socio-economic system)? Traditionally this concept has had a strong biological meaning; therefore, applying it to social science research requires careful consideration.
4. Why should the concept of ecosystem be better suited than, for example, community, networks, etc?

Cooperation between VET providers and other sectors and stakeholders

The question of the importance of the development of networks and collaborations between all stakeholders involved in VET and LLL was raised continuously throughout the discussion. The key points relating to the challenge of making the collaboration between VET providers and other key stakeholders meaningful were addressed and considered during the meeting. One important issue was highlighted: that the nature of the collaboration between the providers/key stakeholders is of a bidirectional relation, not just a responsive one. This means that the channels of communication and cooperation represent a system of shared interactions between practitioners, policy-makers and other key stakeholders. Otherwise, there is concern that there is a risk that the trainers’ and teachers’ perspectives will be lost. One important point that was emphasised is that cooperation should also focus on learning at work and informal learning, which includes a reflection about how work and tasks have to be shaped to foster learning. It is of crucial importance to develop collaboration and build up trust between sectors. In respect of cooperation the following points have been noted:

1. The question of cooperation needs to be considered across all levels (micro, meso and macro), developing strategies and approaches to facilitate the interlinks and connections between these levels.
2. Developing common goals is of utmost importance. Careful planning needs to take into account three key actors (VET institutions, companies or labour market, and VET learners).
3. Involving employers would be a challenge, because they do not always look to upscale their employees either vocationally or personally.
4. The major challenge is that cooperation is important, but also difficult. What is the aim of cooperation in VET? Are employers willing to cooperate if the aim is to promote social inclusion?

Supporting learners

Support for learners needs to be an important goal across all three levels (micro, meso and macro). A shared understanding of learners’ needs, motivations and ambitions needs to be taken into account and addressed through cooperative and communicational structures. VET and LLL should address not only equipping learners with vocational and job-related skills, but also offer them opportunities for lifelong learning and personal development, social inclusion, development of social networks and active citizenship.

Placing learners at the centre of the learning process should be considered a priority of LLL approaches. It is of crucial importance to allow for more student/learner participation in the development of the process (e.g. the development of curricula/standards). As noted, ‘*Putting learners in the centre should become a reality and not just lip service.*’

In undertaking future research, taking into account the individual level (micro level) has been highlighted as an important research approach, i.e. research needs to start at the individual level by interviews (e.g. including questions on individual learning biographies) to understand the problems faced by young people and adults. This can be the basis for further investigations at institutional (meso) and societal (macro) levels .

Recognition of learners' prior skills was emphasised as a strategy that contributes to the development of motivation and confidence and, therefore, this strategy should be incorporated into LLL and VET learning discourses. However, vocational guidance should consolidate both the recognition of past experiences and a '*prospective approach*' (looking ahead in terms of development of skills for the future).

Conclusions

The consideration of these cross-cutting themes indicates that LLL and VET often overlap and involve complex processes, which both influence and are being influenced by ecosystems and ecologies. Cooperation between stakeholders is a crucial component of VET, which is being continuously developed and shaped across the three levels (micro, meso and macro). A socio-ecological approach can contribute to better understanding how communicative ecologies operate through networks that build on these shared understandings in relation to the purposes and aims of VET. Building shared understandings of the needs, capabilities and ambitions of participants in VET is one of the core elements. Key stakeholders (such as teachers and trainers) play a key mediating role in the development of this shared understanding while making inter-connections between the three levels (micro, meso and macro).

Report on the VETNET research workshop
during the third EU Vocational Skills Week in Vienna, 07.11.2018

Vocational education and training across the lifespan

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Introduction

VETNET mission

The Vocational Education and Training Network VETNET is an open network, which welcomes contributions from all over the world as long as they are in line with the goals of VETNET.

VETNET is focusing on research and development in the field of initial, higher and continuing vocational education and training (VET) and learning across the life-span.

The goals of VETNET are to promote research on vocational education and training and to contribute its development by:

- fostering a high quality of research in the field of vocational education and training;
- exploring the relationship between research, policy and practice;
- stimulating the multidisciplinary discussion and dissemination of research results in the European research area and beyond through mutual learning;
- encouraging, establishing and maintaining cooperation between VET researchers and project partnerships in the European research area through, e.g., organising the VETNET programme at the ECER, Crossing Boundaries or Stockholm International Conference; developing international contacts; cooperating with other relevant conferences; publications or by producing electronic or other newsletters;
- maintaining the peer-reviewed VETNET journal IJRNET, the VETNET ECER proceedings and contributing to other international publications; maintaining the community website vetnetsite.org.

VETNET

- maintains a community website on vetnetsite.org;
- has an entry on the EERA website: <https://eera-ecer.de/networks/2-vocational-education-and-training-vetnet/>;
- has a project on [researchgate.net](https://www.researchgate.net/project/IRNVET-VETNET-International-Research-Network-in-Vocational-Education-and-Training-VETNET-European-Research-Network-in-Vocational-Education-and-Training): <https://www.researchgate.net/project/IRNVET-VETNET-International-Research-Network-in-Vocational-Education-and-Training-VETNET-European-Research-Network-in-Vocational-Education-and-Training>;
- has a community on <https://zenodo.org/communities/vetnet/> to host the conference proceedings.

Aim and scope of the workshop

The topic of the researchers' workshop at the EU Vocational Skills Week 2018 in Vienna was: "Vocational education and training across the lifespan".

All participants contributed to the workshop with a short abstract on the topic "Vocational education and training across the lifespan" and a short bibliography.

Four presentations were selected as impetus presentations. These were short presentations by the authors to stimulate the discussion in the workshop. After the discussion, the presenters of the impetus presentations wrote short minutes on the discussion during the workshop. The impetus presentations and minutes are covered in this report.

Programme of the workshop

Introduction

- Dr Christof Nägele
Senior Researcher, University of Applied Sciences and Arts, Northwestern Switzerland
- Dr Dr h.c. Michael Gessler
Professor, Institute Technology and Education, University of Bremen
- Mantas Sekmokas
Policy Officer, European Commission, DG Employment, Social Affairs and Inclusion

Impetus Presentations

Lifelong learning and VET: towards understanding the influence of societal eco-systems on learning across the lifespan

- Dr Natalia (Natasha) Kersh
UCL Institute of Education, University of London
- Dr Karen Evans
Professor Emeritus, UCL Institute of Education, University of London

Apprenticeship Reform in France

- Eric Dumartin
Vice-President of Fongecif Île-de-France, Vice-President of IAE Paris I Panthéon Sorbonne

The VET Skills Cycle and the Formation of Construction Management Skills in Ireland

- Eoghan Ó Murchadha
Assistant Head of Department of Craft, Design, Construction and Apprenticeship, Dún Laoghaire Further Education Institute in Dublin

The Role of VET on the Inclusion of Marginalized Young People and Adult People from a Lifelong Perspective across the Lifespan

- Dr Patricia Olmos Rueda
Professor, Autonomous University of Barcelona (UAB)
- Dr Fernando Marhuenda
Professor, University of Valencia

Outlook

- Dr Dr h.c. Michael Gessler & Dr Christof Nägele